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‘We’re All in This Together?’ A Survey Experiment on the Perceived Legitimacy of Region-Specific Crisis Interventions in Germany and the Netherlands

Lars Brummel

Institute of Public Administration, Faculty of Governance and Global Affairs, Leiden University, Leiden, the Netherlands

Correspondence: Lars Brummel (l.brummel@fgga.leidenuniv.nl)**Received:** 7 January 2025 | **Revised:** 6 August 2025 | **Accepted:** 4 September 2025**Funding:** This work was financially supported by the Horizon 2020 Framework Program within the project LEGITIMULT [Grant Number HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01, GA Nr. 101061550].

ABSTRACT

In responding to crises, governments often need to enact restrictions on the freedoms of citizens that might be perceived as intrusive and unfair. Yet, government interventions need to retain legitimacy in the eyes of citizens. We study the perceived legitimacy of pandemic crisis interventions with a focus on the effects of multi-level governance and region-specific interventions. Such territorially-differentiated measures are often appropriate for effective crisis responses, but they raise concerns about equal treatment. Our pre-registered survey experiments run on quota-representative national samples in Germany and the Netherlands ($N = 2252$) find no evidence in support of the conjecture that citizens perceive nation-wide crisis interventions as more legitimate than region-specific measures. The level of government making the decision matters very little for the legitimacy of the interventions. Restrictions enacted by the national government are slightly more accepted than those decided regionally in the Netherlands, but there is no such difference in Germany.

1 | Introduction

When crises—such as natural disasters, terrorist attacks, and epidemics—strike, they pose significant challenges to the problem-solving capacity of governments. Governments are expected to respond in a way that is adequate and effective, but also legitimate (Christensen et al. 2016). Legitimacy is crucial for crisis management, because it forms the basis for citizens to voluntarily accept and comply with emergency rules that are implemented by governments (Mizrahi et al. 2023). As Boin et al. (2021), 56) argue, “when collective behavior is the key to effective management of the crisis, legitimacy is probably the most important asset that governments can possess”.

However, the legitimacy of a crisis response can be seriously challenged, because governments face difficult decisional trade-offs in their crisis management activities (Boin et al. 2005;

Moynihan 2009; Rosenthal et al. 1989). During crises, governments often have to restrict temporarily the individual rights and liberties of some citizens, weighing different values and interests in the process (Amirkhanyan et al. 2023; Davis and Silver 2004). They also need to decide on the allocation of scarce time and resources prioritizing some categories of citizens over others (Mazepus and van Leeuwen 2020).

Such tradeoffs and decisions can be exceedingly complex when a crisis results in asymmetrical shocks for different parts of a country. Many of the modern-day crises are not restricted to a single place at a single moment in time, but transcend multiple political, geographical and/or temporal boundaries (Boin 2019; Broekema et al. 2024). When a crisis has differential impact across regions, governments have to decide on how to deal with these regional differences. Region-specific crisis interventions can be an effective and flexible strategy. However, cross-regional

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differences in government interventions can compound the difficulties of keeping the crisis response legitimate, as they raise additional concerns about equal treatment.

The Covid-19 pandemic provides a well-known case of a recent large-scale crisis in which governments were presented with the dilemma between nation-wide and region-specific crisis interventions. Although many governments implemented nation-wide lockdowns during the initial phase of the pandemic (Jugl 2023; Toshkov et al. 2022), regionally-targeted interventions, such as regional lockdowns, curfews and school closures, were enforced in several countries (including Belgium, Germany, Spain, and the United Kingdom) in the later stages of the crisis.

Given the practical relevance of region-specific interventions and the challenges they pose for the legitimacy of government crisis responses, it is crucial that we examine how such measures are actually perceived by the citizens. We have relatively limited understanding in the crisis management literature of what citizens consider to be a legitimate response of governmental authorities to crisis situations (cf. Lenz 2024; Mazepus and van Leeuwen 2020). But are citizens willing to accept stringent crisis measures in their own region that restrict their own individual rights and liberties, while citizens in other parts of a country are exempted from similar restrictions?

In this article, we study how citizens evaluate the legitimacy of region-specific crisis interventions in the context of a transboundary crisis, such as an epidemic outbreak. Based on insights from distributive justice theory, we first theorize how regional differences in crisis management relate to public perceptions of legitimacy. We further advance a theoretical argument about how multi-level governance could impact the legitimacy of region-specific crisis interventions.

We test the theoretical hypotheses we develop in a survey experiment that investigates citizens' legitimacy perceptions of region-specific crisis interventions. Our fictional scenario discusses the implementation of a lockdown in response to a novel virus outbreak. In the design, we manipulate two factors: the level of government that implements the measure (national vs. regional government) and the degree of uniformity of the measure (national uniformity vs. regional diversity). We field our experimental survey among quota-representative national samples in two countries: Germany and the Netherlands ($N = 2252$). Importantly, Germany is a federal state, while the Netherlands is a unitary one, which allows us to study how the structure of government moderates the effects on region-specific crisis responses on perceived legitimacy.

Our findings reveal that citizens in both Germany and the Netherlands do not consider national and uniform crisis interventions as more legitimate than region-specific measures. The level of government implementing these interventions — national or regional—has minimal impact on perceived legitimacy. In the Netherlands, crisis-related restrictions imposed by the national government are only slightly more accepted than those made at the regional level, whereas in Germany, no such difference is observed.

Our experimental study holds both scientific and practical relevance. We extend the emerging literature on the interplay between crisis management and political-administrative legitimacy (Lee 2022; Lenz 2024; Mazepus and van Leeuwen 2020) by focusing on the *territorial* dimensions of transboundary crisis management. We further contribute to the multi-level governance literature by examining whether the *level* of government that implements a decision (national vs. regional government) relates to citizens' legitimacy perceptions of crisis interventions. Although multi-level governance has been considered as a relevant factor for the timing, efficiency and effectiveness of crisis responses (Carroll et al. 2025; Jugl 2024; Salazar-Morales et al. 2024), the role of governmental levels for shaping legitimacy beliefs remains underexplored.

Our findings are also relevant for the practice of multi-level crisis management, because various experts have proposed region-specific crisis interventions as a better strategic choice for controlling (future) epidemics (Dekker et al. 2023; Long et al. 2023; Roux et al. 2023), as well as environmental crises and natural disasters (Hanssen et al. 2013; Termeer et al. 2011). In this context, understanding how citizens assess the legitimacy of such region-specific crisis responses becomes crucial for the potential success of these strategies.

2 | Theoretical Framework

2.1 | Crises, Legitimacy and Legitimacy Beliefs

In this article, we study the legitimacy of government interventions during a crisis, which we define following Rosenthal et al. (1989), 10) as “a serious threat to the basic structures or the fundamental values and norms of a social system, which—under time pressure and highly uncertain circumstances—necessitates making critical decisions”. Crises consist of three main elements: threat, urgency, and uncertainty (see also Boin et al. 2005; McConnell 2003; Moynihan 2009). Because of these characteristics, crises pose significant challenges to the problem-solving *capacity* of governments. In addition, the crisis management literature has increasingly highlighted the challenges associated with crafting *legitimate* responses to crisis events (Christensen et al. 2016; see also Lenz 2024; Mazepus and van Leeuwen 2020; Mizrahi et al. 2023)

Legitimacy is however a contested concept (Beetham 2013; Buchanan 2002; Schoon 2022) with a multitude of meanings. As a *normative* concept, legitimacy reflects theoretical and prescriptive considerations about the moral set of standards against which political authority should be judged. In contrast, a *descriptive* (or empirical) approach to legitimacy focuses on the subjective beliefs or judgments of citizens about whether a political authority and/or its actions are “appropriate, proper, and just” (Tyler 2006, 375). Both approaches to legitimacy can be relevant for the study of crisis governance. Whereas normative interpretations suggest standards governance should aspire to in times of crisis, a descriptive approach to legitimacy uncovers factors and processes that make crisis management acceptable for citizens. In this study, we adopt a descriptive notion to

legitimacy and focus on citizens' subjective evaluations or perceptions of the legitimacy of crisis management.

Following a descriptive approach, legitimacy reflects a concept that is difficult to measure directly, and there is an ongoing debate about the way in which legitimacy should be operationalized (Schoon 2022; Thomas 2014). In public administration and political science scholarship, legitimacy has often been operationalized with references to perceived fairness, decision acceptance, and trust (see e.g. Brummel and de Blok 2024; De Fine Licht et al. 2014; Esaiasson et al. 2019; Mazepus and van Leeuwen 2020; Werner and Marien 2022). However, the relationship between legitimacy and trust, in particular, has been contested. Although trust in institutions is often used as an indicator for institutional legitimacy, several authors challenged this approach and highlighted important conceptual differences between legitimacy and trust (see e.g. Kaina 2008; Thomassen et al. 2017).

From a crisis management perspective, we argue that there are different operationalizations of legitimacy that are more consequential for our focus on crisis interventions. First, in the social psychological literature, *compliance* is often used as an indicator for legitimacy (Jackson et al. 2012; Levi et al. 2009; Tyler 2006), capturing the extent to which individuals feel an obligation to obey rules and laws (Tyler and Jackson 2014). Such an obligation is not rooted primarily in coercion or material incentives, but in the belief that authorities are rightful and their directives are normatively justified (Grimes 2006). In this view, legitimacy captures the beliefs that foster willingness to obey, drawing on internalized norms that make people feel they “ought to” comply. As Tyler (1990) argues, such beliefs generate normative commitment not only reflected in personal willingness to comply, but in a broader feeling “that the authority enforcing the law has the right to dictate behavior” (p. 4). In crisis settings—where enforcement capacity can be constrained—this kind of voluntary compliance can become an important resource for effective governance (Boin et al. 2021).

Second, the *acceptability of protests*—and violent protests in particular—can be an important indicator of a loss in the legitimacy of crisis interventions. Crises often tend to trigger large-scale streets protests against the governmental (mis)management of the crisis (Grasso and Giugni 2016; Kriesi and Oana 2023). When citizens consider governmental actions as illegitimate, this is likely to increase the acceptance of protests and even violence. As Gilley (2006, 508) suggests, when citizens believe that violence in protests can be tolerated, this could be “a good effect indicator of justification failures” on behalf of their governments. But also the acceptance of non-violent protests can be a sign of weakening legitimacy. In the sociological literature, legitimacy is often associated with a “lack of evident opposition” to rules and decisions (Schoon 2022, 481). From this perspective, legitimacy is derived from the fact that the appropriateness of rules and decisions is ‘taken for granted’ and the existence of authority has not been questioned, but rather perceived as necessary or inevitable (see also Johnson et al. 2006; Suchman 1995; Tost 2011). Protests signal a loss of passive acceptance and hence a questioning of the decision's legitimacy. To the contrary, when citizens view such protests against crisis measures as unacceptable, this could suggest that there is a shared

belief that government actions, although potentially imperfect, are legitimate and necessary to address a crisis.

2.2 | Crisis Management and Crisis Management Trade-Offs

In their crisis responses, governments could face various decisional dilemmas or *trade-offs* that can impact their perceived legitimacy (Lenz 2024). These dilemmas could, for example, relate to whether governments should follow legal standards and procedures or rather respond flexibly to a crisis, or how they should decide on the allocation of scarce resources (see also Mazepus and van Leeuwen 2020). For many crises, such as terrorist attacks and epidemic outbreaks, governments further have to weigh collective security and safety against individual rights and liberties (Gearty 2013). Governments can, for example, introduce restrictive measures in order to protect the safety of the community that come at the cost of individual freedoms (Amirkhanyan et al. 2023; Belle and Cantarelli 2022; Davis and Silver 2004; Dragu 2011).

Many of these dilemmas are further complicated when a crisis is transboundary in nature and crosses geographical and political borders (Blondin and Boin 2020; Broekema et al. 2024). Because of their cross-territorial dimensions, transboundary crises can impact different towns, regions, and/or communities in diverging ways (Ansell et al. 2010, 196), which presents governmental authorities with two additional challenges. In *the first place*, they have to decide on how to deal with differences in the regional consequences of a crisis. In *the second place*, it becomes a relevant question which level of government should be in charge of dealing with the consequences of a crisis, because responsibilities can be distributed across multiple governmental levels, including both national and regional authorities (Boin 2019, 95).

A territorially-differentiated approach could shape citizens' perceptions of the legitimacy of the response. Moreover, the question of which level of government holds authority during a transboundary crisis can further affect legitimacy perceptions, especially if coordination between levels seems disjointed or if responsibilities are perceived as misaligned with the crisis's impacts.

3 | Hypotheses

How do citizens evaluate the legitimacy of region-specific crisis interventions and the role of regional governments in crisis management? Here, we focus on restrictive crisis interventions that limit personal freedoms (i.e., regional lockdowns), as these types of interventions are often discussed in the crisis management literature and provide clear challenges for guaranteeing legitimacy. Recent studies suggest that citizens accept restrictive crisis interventions that contribute to collective security, but become more critical when interventions strongly affect their individual rights and liberties (Amirkhanyan et al. 2023; Belle and Cantarelli 2022).

Based on distributive justice theory, we expect that acceptance of restrictive crisis interventions will be smaller for region-

specific measures compared to nation-wide measures—that is when restrictive measures are only applied to specific regions within a country, instead of the entire territory of a nation. Distributive justice reflects the perceived fairness of the distribution of resources and burdens within a political community (Fleischacker 2005; Nozick 2012). Distributive justice theory suggests that citizens evaluate the legitimacy of governmental actions and decisions by reflecting on their own situation in comparison the situation of others (Folger 1977; Sunshine and Tyler 2003). When citizens perceive strong relative deprivation—or, in other words, when they believe that their own burden is higher compared to others (Crosby 1976; Smith and Pettigrew 2014), this might generate feelings of distributive injustice and challenge their perceptions of legitimacy.

Meanwhile, distributive justice theory suggests that people's views on fairness are shaped by their specific situations and that their preferred principles of distributive fairness—equality, equity (desert), or need—can vary based on a situation itself and the information that is available (Miller 1992). Rather than promoting equal treatment, region-specific crisis interventions can therefore be perceived as fair, as they target regions that are most in need of protection and intervention. In the context of natural disasters, Mazepus and van Leeuwen (2020), for example find that a needs-based allocation of resources contribute to citizens' perceptions of the legitimacy of crisis management (but see also Lenz 2024, for contrasting findings).

In the context of *restrictive* crisis interventions, we suggest that the principle of *equality* is the most relevant principle for the legitimacy of region-specific, particularly when one's own region is affected by these measures. Following Crosby's (1976, 89) relative deprivation theory, we argue that region-specific restrictions create “a discrepant comparison with a similar other concerning a desired good or opportunity” that could stimulate a feeling of relative deprivation, potentially undermining beliefs of legitimacy. Hence, we expect that citizens would consider region-specific, crisis-related restrictions to be less legitimate, compared to nation-wide measures. Accordingly, our first hypothesis (H1) posits that *citizens will consider a uniform, nation-wide lockdown in the entire territory of their country as more legitimate than regional diversity regarding lockdowns that includes a lockdown in their own region.*

From a multi-level governance perspective, the legitimacy of crisis interventions can differ depending on the level of government that takes a decision. When a major crisis hits and crosses political and territorial boundaries, different layers of government can be involved in a transboundary crisis response, particularly when the characteristics of a crisis interacts with the complex division of powers between national and subnational units of government (Blondin and Boin 2020). As a consequence, multiple actors and levels of governments could claim responsibility for policies targeted at addressing the crisis (Carroll et al. 2025).

In our study, we focus on whether citizens differentiate in their legitimacy beliefs on crisis interventions that are implemented by either (1) the national or (2) the regional government. Multi-level governance scholarship suggests that citizens hold different political attitudes and evaluations toward different levels of governments (Fitzgerald and Wolak 2016; Proszowska

et al. 2023; Schakel and Brown 2022). However, this dynamic can operate in various directions. On the one hand, there is research that indicates that citizens have strong preferences for regional authority, both in unitary and federal states (Henderson 2014; Henderson et al. 2013; Schakel and Smith 2022). In parallel, crisis management scholarship posits that the perceived legitimacy of interventions may be enhanced when decisions are made by the level of government closest to the people (Boin 2019; Hegele and Schnabel 2021). When a regional government takes the lead in a crisis response, citizens may interpret this as a signal that local needs and circumstances are being adequately considered.

On the other hand, in the context of large-scale, nation-wide crises, citizens might prefer to transfer responsibilities into the hands of their political leaders at the national level, because they consider the national government to be the most capable actor to deal with the consequences of such a large crisis (see, e.g., Boin 2019, 97). Within transboundary crisis management, there is a strong tendency to centralize decision-making responsibilities at the national level in times of crises (Boin et al. 2005; Christensen et al. 2016; 't Hart et al. 1993), and citizens might have internalized this so-called ‘centralization thesis’.

Meanwhile, the ‘institutional hypothesis’ (Schakel and Brown 2022, 311) suggests that cross-national differences shape the extent to which citizens view various levels of government as legitimate actors in crisis management. Countries vary substantially in the degree of subnational authority granted to regional governments (Hooghe and Marks 2003). In federal and decentralized systems, citizens are more likely to expect regional governments to assume responsibility for a broad array of policy fields, compared to unitary and centralized systems (Henderson et al. 2013; Schakel and Smith 2022). We are therefore open to the option that citizens consider crisis measures of regional governments as more legitimate, but only in contexts where these governments play a significant role in public policy provision.

Given these contrasting views in the literature, we present two competing hypotheses regarding the effects of level of government (national vs. regional government) on the perceived legitimacy of crisis-related interventions. *Hypothesis 2 (H2)* posits that *citizens will consider a lockdown as more legitimate when it is implemented by a regional government, as compared to a national government.* In contrast, *Hypothesis 2a (H2a)* states that *citizens will consider a lockdown as more legitimate when it is implemented by a national government, as compared to a regional government.*

Particularly, for region-specific crisis interventions, we hypothesize that citizens consider a decision made by the regional government as more legitimate compared to one implemented by the national government. When a regional government implements a regional measure, this is often a consequence of *design*. When a national government however implements a regional measure, this can be interpreted as a consequence of *deliberate choice*, thereby potentially triggering citizens' perceptions of relative deprivation and distributive *injustice* (cf. Fleischacker 2005; Miller 1992). Regional governments might be perceived to be better able and more legitimate in dealing with region-specific challenges. Whereas the national level of

government is expected to deliver state-wide policies in accordance with principles of uniformity and solidarity, citizens expect regional governments to offer tailor-made policy decisions that are more responsive to the local needs and circumstances of regional communities (Henderson et al. 2013; Schakel and Smith 2022; Weissert and Jones 2015).

Therefore, we expect an interaction effect between the level of government that implements a decision (regional vs. national government) and the regional differentiation in crisis-related interventions (uniformity vs. diversity). Hence, our *third and final hypothesis (H3)* is formulated as: *When the national government implements a region-specific lockdown, citizens will consider a region-specific lockdown as less legitimate than when it is implemented by the regional government.*

4 | Methods

4.1 | Experimental Design and Scenario

To test the theoretical hypotheses developed in the previous section, we designed and conducted a pre-registered vignette experiment.¹ The study adopts a 2×2 between-subjects randomized experimental design in which each respondent is confronted with only one treatment (Atzmüller and Steiner 2010).

The empirical context for our vignette experiment is an epidemic outbreak. In our experimental set-up, we first presented our respondents with a hypothetical scenario in which a highly contagious and deadly virus is spreading rapidly in their country. To combat the spread of the virus, respondents read that strict rules will be implemented: they are no longer allowed to leave their houses unless it is absolutely necessary, and schools and businesses will be closed.

We manipulate two factors: (a) the *level of government* that enacts the restrictions and (b) the *policy uniformity*. Either (1) the national or (2) the regional government takes the decision to implement strict rules in order to contain the spread of the virus. To strengthen the experimental realism of the vignettes, we mention the particular name of the region in which the respondent resides, which we obtained from a previous survey response. Policy uniformity also takes two values: the measures are either (1) similar in all regions of the country [national

uniformity] or (2) stricter in specific regions, including the region of the respondent, than in other parts of the country [regional diversity]. Hence, the design features a total of $2 \times 2 = 4$ conditions. The four different versions of the vignette, translated to English, can be found in Appendix I.

We have chosen for a scenario of an epidemic outbreak because it reflects one of the clearest examples of a transboundary crisis, with a strong territorial dimension (Ansell et al. 2010; Boin et al. 2021). Our scenario closely mirrors real-world events, particularly the Covid-19 pandemic that occurred globally from 2020 to 2022, thereby contributing to the ecological validity of our experiment. Also, the inclusion of specific details, such as restrictions on leaving homes and the closure of schools and businesses, enhances the realism of our vignette, because these measures were taken in many different countries across the globe in response to the pandemic (Jugl 2023; Toshkov et al. 2022).²

Furthermore, our different treatments capture plausible configurations of the level of decision-making authority with the degree of policy uniformity. In the context of the Covid-19 pandemic, national governments have enforced nation-wide lockdowns, as well as regional lockdowns. In various countries, regional governments were further responsible for introducing restrictive measures, such as lockdowns or school closures (see e.g. Kuhlmann et al. 2021). Although regional decision-making might challenge national uniformity of public policies, this is not an implausible combination, because inter-governmental coordination between regional governments can contribute to a consistent set of measures across the entire territory of a country—as it was, for example, the case for the initial response of the German *Länder* at the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic (Hegele and Schnabel 2021). For all four experimental conditions, Table 1 provides an overview of real-world examples of governmental responses in Europe (including Germany and the Netherlands) to the Covid-19 pandemic.

4.2 | Country Selection

We collected data from respondents in two different countries: Germany and the Netherlands. With our country selection, we are able to test our theoretical hypotheses in two countries with different multi-level governance structures. Germany is a federal state comprising 16 federal states (*Länder*), each with its

TABLE 1 | Examples of different policy responses to the Covid-19 pandemic in Europe.

	Level of decision-making: National government	Level of decision-making: regional government
National uniformity of measures	Night curfew in The Netherlands, January 2021 Lockdown in Switzerland, March 2020	Closures of bars and restaurants in Germany, March 2020
Regional diversity of measures	Emergency brake policy in Germany, April—June 2021 Regional lockdown in northern parts of Italy, March 2020 Zone-specific lockdowns in Paris and other French regions, March 2021	Night curfew in Bavaria (Germany), March 2020 Night curfew in Antwerp (Belgium), August 2020 Regional lockdown in Catalonia (Spain), July 2021

own constitution and government. The German federal system entails a clear distribution of powers and responsibilities between the federal and state governments, in which the state governments hold considerable legislative powers on a wide array of policy issues, including the management of (health) crises (Gunlicks 2003).

Conversely, the Netherlands is an unitary state, in which the regional level of government exists out of 12 different provinces (or *provincies* in Dutch). Within the Dutch political system, the legislative authority of provincial governments is considerably more restricted compared to the German *Länder*. While Dutch provinces have important policy responsibilities with regards to spatial planning and infrastructure development, their legislative powers are largely limited by national legislation, and they rely heavily on national policies and funding. As a consequence, provinces are a rather abstract and invisible tier of government for many citizens, while the central government and local authorities are perceived as the key political and administrative levels in the Netherlands (Groenleer and Hendriks 2020; Hulst 2005).³

Both countries were further selected based on their differences in multilevel political responses during the Covid-19 pandemic. In Germany, the *Länder* were provided considerable autonomy to decide on restrictive measures from the onset of the pandemic (Hegele and Schnabel 2021). Later in 2021, the federal government introduced the *Notbremse* (“emergency brake”) policy, which established a uniform framework of standardized thresholds based on the 7-day infection incidence rate, mandating region-specific restrictions when infection levels exceeded specific limits (Bundestag 2021). In the Netherlands, the pandemic response was primarily coordinated at the national level, although local and regional (i.e. safety regions) authorities were granted some discretion to adapt national measures to regional circumstances, especially early in the pandemic (Pattyn et al. 2020). Their autonomy was however constrained once the central government adopted new pandemic legislation in December 2020 (Rijksoverheid 2021). Importantly, the provincial level of government had a minor role in the crisis response to the pandemic. Although region-specific crisis interventions have been discussed in the Netherlands, they were rarely implemented and there were no major regional differences in policy restrictions during the pandemic (Van den Berg et al. 2021).

Because of these differences, Dutch and German citizens might hold different expectations on the role of different governmental levels in crisis management. The case selection allows us to explore whether citizens react differently in federal and unitary states, and with different past experiences with multilevel crisis management, which contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the role of multi-level governance structures in shaping legitimacy beliefs about crisis interventions.

4.3 | Data Collection and Sample

In both Germany and the Netherlands, respondents were selected and recruited by the survey company Bilendi using

their large online panels. The experiment was administrated in German and in Dutch. Data collection took place between April 27th, 2024 and May 15th, 2024. We used demographic quotas in order to create samples representative of the countries' adult populations with regard to gender, age and education. Appendix II reports the demographic distribution of the samples for both countries.

In total, our final sample consists of $N = 1120$ participants from the Netherlands and $N = 1132$ participants from Germany. To maximize data quality, we excluded from the set of complete responses a small number of participants ($N = 28$ in the case of the Netherlands and $N = 25$ in Germany) who completed the survey unrealistically fast (within 3 min, given a median completion times of 7.6/7.9 min and first quartile at 5.7/5.9 min). Participants were only able to complete the survey if they passed a simple attention check.

4.4 | Outcome Variables and Measurement

Our dependent variable is the legitimacy of crisis interventions as perceived by citizens. We focus on two different aspects of legitimacy: (1) compliance and (2) protest acceptability. *Compliance* is often considered as an expression of legitimacy (Grimes 2006; Tyler 2006), reflecting citizens' willingness to adhere to rules because they perceive them as legitimate and appropriate. We measured compliance by two survey items: “Would you adhere to these rules?” [1: Not at all, 5: Completely] and “Would you find it acceptable if citizens disregard these measures?” [1: Not acceptable at all, 5: Completely acceptable]. As such, our measure of compliance reflects respondents' own intention to comply with restrictive measures, as well as their attitudes toward others' disregard for such restrictions.⁴ Our two-item measure of *compliance* showed a relatively high correlation of $r = 0.69$. We take the average of the two items, after we invert the scale of the second question to have the same polarity. For robustness reasons, we further present the item-level analyses in our Supplementary information.

The second aspect of legitimacy that we study is the *acceptability of protests*. Specifically, protest acceptability gauges the extent to which individuals believe it is justified for citizens to strongly and openly oppose government measures, possibly resorting to violence, which indicates their levels of perceived illegitimacy of decisions made by authorities (Gilley 2006). To measure protest acceptability, we first presented respondents with a short intervention in which they read about regional protests against the lockdown measures, including an image of protests (see Appendix I). After the second intervention, respondents were asked to answer the following two questions that both focus on protest acceptability, also including an item on the unacceptability of the use of violence during protests: “Do you think it is fair that people protest against the new rules? [1: Not fair at all, 5: Completely fair] and “Would you find it acceptable that some people resort to violence against the authorities in these protests?” [1: Not acceptable at all, 5: Completely acceptable]. We invert the polarity (so that higher values indicate higher legitimacy of the government interventions).

There was only a modest correlation between both items, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.25$, suggesting that these items capture potentially independent attitudes. Because of the weaker internal consistency, we only conducted item-level analyses for the two protest unacceptability items. We present the findings for our first item (acceptability of protests in general) in the main text and we report the findings for our second item (acceptability of violent protests) in the Supplementary information.

4.5 | Analytical Approach

We test all hypotheses using the same experimental manipulations and modeling strategy on both outcome variables. We estimate linear probability models of the various facets of perceived legitimacy as a function of the experimental manipulations and their interactions (Models 1a, 1b, 2a and 2b), separately for each of the two countries in our sample. For reasons of clarity and interpretability, we slightly deviate from the pre-registration and present ANOVA tables to assess the overall contribution of each factor and interaction to the outcome, along with plots of marginal effects. This change reflects the fact that in the presence of interactions, ANOVA offers a clearer and more appropriate way to evaluate the significance of each factor as a whole and is also more aligned with the logic of our factorial experimental design.

For transparency and completeness, we include the full dummy-coded OLS regression tables in the Supplementary information, as originally planned (Tables A3, A3.1, A3.2, A4.1 and A4.2). For exploratory purposes, we add respondents' demographic characteristics and an indicator distinguishing ideologically extreme respondents from the rest in these

models (Models A1a, A2b, A2a and A2b reported in the Supplementary information).

5 | Results

In this section we provide details on the main regression models and illustrate the results with plots of the predicted probabilities of *Compliance* and *Protest unacceptability* for each experimental condition. In the Supplementary information we provide descriptive statistics of the number of respondents in each experimental group and the means of the outcome variables per group (Tables A1, A1.1, A1.2, A2.1 and A2.2). We also report variations of the main regression models with additional covariates in the Supplementary information.

Table 2 shows the results from the analyses of variance (ANOVA) of the linear regression models of compliance as a function of the experimental treatments and their interaction, separately for Germany and the Netherlands. The coefficients from the regression models themselves are reported in the Supplementary information and are illustrated in Figure 1.

Overall, we find no significant differences in compliance across the policy uniformity and diversity conditions in any of the two countries considered individually. The average levels of compliance are similar for policy measures that concern the entire territory of the country and that concern only certain regions. This is also visible from Figure 1, which plots the predicted probabilities of compliance for different factor levels. Hence, we find no support for Hypothesis 1.

When we examine the effect of the decision authority, we find some support for H2a in the Netherlands, where compliance is

TABLE 2 | Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results.

Model	Source of variation	Df	Sum of Sq	Mean Sq	F-value	p-value
1a Compliance (Germany)	Uniform	1	1.34	1.34	1.01	0.31
	National	1	0.21	0.21	0.16	0.69
	Uniform × national	1	5.94	5.94	4.51	0.03
	Residuals	1128	1486.77	1.32		
1b Compliance (Netherlands)	Uniform	1	3.00	3.00	2.62	0.11
	National	1	7.39	7.39	6.47	0.01
	Uniform × national	1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.98
	Residuals	1116	1275.72	1.14		
2a Protest unacceptability (Germany)	Uniform	1	2.23	2.23	1.38	0.24
	National	1	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.84
	Uniform × national	1	0.50	0.50	0.31	0.58
	Residuals	1128	1820.35	1.61		
2b Protest unacceptability (Netherlands)	Uniform	1	0.09	0.09	0.06	0.81
	National	1	4.43	4.43	2.67	0.10
	Uniform × national	1	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.90
	Residuals	1116	1854.60	1.66		

FIGURE 1 | Predicted level of compliance.

significantly higher for measures decided nationally compared to regionally decided measures, but not in Germany. There is no evidence that compliance is higher for regionally-adopted measures in any of the two countries, in contradiction to the expectation in Hypothesis 2.

When we examine the conditional effect hypothesized in H3, we find evidence for an interaction between the uniformity of the government measures and the decision authority in Germany. When region-specific measures are adopted, compliance is higher when the national government decides compared to when the regional governments decide. When uniform measures are adopted, the compliance is higher if the regional governments decide compared to the national government. This is in direct contradiction to our hypothesis, which predicted the opposite pattern. In the Netherlands, there is no evidence for an interaction.

We should note that the effects, even when statistically significant are very small in size relative to the standard deviation of compliance (which is 1.07 in the Dutch sample and 1.15 in the German one). The differences in the predicted values for the different experimental conditions are less than 0.30, whereas compliance varies on a scale between 1 and 5 (note that the y-axes in Figure 1 are truncated).

We find that compliance is significantly higher in the Netherlands than in Germany. This is noteworthy, even though we did not hypothesize any cross-country differences in the average level of perceived legitimacy of the government measures. Comparing the pattern of responses across the two

countries in Figure 1, what stands out is the much lower level of compliance with uniform measures when adopted by the national government in Germany compared to the Netherlands.

The experimental results are not sensitive to the inclusion of demographic covariates (see Table A3 in the Supplementary information). For exploratory purposes, we also include a variable capturing the political ideology of the respondent as a predictor. It turns out that people who are more ideologically extreme on a progressive-conservative scale in the Netherlands and who are more ideologically extreme on a left-right scale in Germany are less likely to express compliance. Despite its significant main effects, there is no evidence that political ideology moderates any of the effects of the experimental treatments.

The interpretation of our results does not drastically change when we look at the item-specific analyses in the Supplementary information (Appendix IV, Table A5). For the Netherlands, we observe that the effect of policy uniformity becomes significant for our measure of respondents' self-reported intent to comply. This might suggest that Dutch citizens are more willing to adhere to uniform measures compared to diverse measures (in line with H1), although we should note that this significant difference only reflects a 0.16-point increase on a five-point scale.

Compliance is an important aspect of perceived legitimacy, but what also matters is whether people find peaceful and violent protests against government measures acceptable or not. Therefore, the second part of our empirical analyses

look into the effect of the experimental treatments on protest unacceptability.

For protest acceptability in general, Models 2a and 2b in Table 2 show the results from the analysis of variance of the regression models. Figure 2 plots the predictions for protest unacceptability based on these models. According to the results, there is not much evidence in support of H1 about the effect of uniform versus regionally-diverse measures.

Looking at the effect of the decision authority, we further see no differences between measures adopted by the national government and those adopted by regional governments. In the Netherlands, protest against measures from the national government is considered slightly less acceptable, but this effect is only significant at $p < 0.1$. In Germany, we do not find any meaningful differences. There is no evidence for an interaction between the two experimental conditions in any of the two countries. Protest unacceptability is significantly higher in the Netherlands compared to Germany, especially for national measures. Political ideology is significantly related to protest unacceptability in Germany only, where ideologically extreme respondents are more likely to find (violent) protests against the measures unacceptable.

Finally, Table A6 reports findings with regards to the acceptability of violent protests. In Germany, respondents consider the use of violence in protests to be less acceptable when measures are implemented by the regional government. In the Netherlands, violent protests are perceived as less acceptable in response to uniform measures. Although these findings are only based on a single-item measure and should therefore be

interpreted with caution, acceptance of violent protests can serve as an important signal of declining legitimacy. Factors contributing to the acceptability of violent protests however appear to vary between Germany and the Netherlands.

6 | Conclusion and Discussion

Crises often cross territorial boundaries, impacting multiple areas either simultaneously or consecutively, transcending single political jurisdictions such as municipalities, regions, and/or countries. This transboundary nature complicates crisis management, raising questions about the legitimacy of interventions and responses (Broekema et al. 2024). Our experimental study investigated how citizens perceive the legitimacy of region-specific versus uniform, nation-wide crisis interventions, and whether the level of government enacting those decisions—regional or national—shapes these perceptions. We focused on two key indicators of legitimacy: compliance and protest acceptability.

Our experimental study reveals two important insights. Firstly, our findings show that citizens do not perceive nation-wide and uniform crisis interventions as more legitimate (in the way that we have operationalized legitimacy) than region-specific measures. Although an important question remains to what extent our findings are applicable to real-life settings, this offers at least an indication that territorial differentiation of crisis interventions are not inherently perceived as less legitimate, as compared to nation-wide and uniform measures. Secondly, we find that the level of government responsible for deciding on

FIGURE 2 | Predicted level of protest unacceptability.

crisis interventions—whether national or regional—has only a small impact on the perceived legitimacy of those interventions. In Germany, there are no significant differences in the perceived legitimacy of crisis interventions between both levels of government. For the Netherlands, we observe that citizens attribute slightly more legitimacy to crisis interventions that are decided by the national government than those decided regionally (in line with H2a). However, this effect appears to be rather small.

As such, our findings challenge the theoretical expectation derived from distributive justice theory (cf. Fleischacker 2005; Miller 1992) that uniform and nation-wide measures would be inherently perceived as fairer or more legitimate. In Germany as well as in the Netherlands, our findings point out that region-specific crisis interventions are perceived as almost equally legitimate as uniform measures. A possible explanation could be that citizens do not evaluate distributive fairness of region-specific interventions based on a principle of equality, but rather perceive these regional restrictions as legitimate because they reflect principles of *equity* and/or *need*. In line with relative deprivation theory, this could further impact citizens' sense of relative deprivation, as relative deprivation tend to be most strongly when citizens believe that an equal distribution of outcomes is both desirable and feasible (Crosby 1976). As such, our findings do not necessarily contradict distributive justice theory, but keep the option open that citizens may prioritize other aspects of distributive fairness (instead of equality) when evaluating the legitimacy of region-specific crisis interventions.

Meanwhile, the role of multi-level governance in shaping perceptions of legitimacy appears to be limited. Whereas crisis management scholarship has emphasized how centralization could affect timing and effectiveness of crisis responses ('t Hart et al. 1993; see also Jugl 2023; Toshkov et al. 2022), our study shows that the governmental level responding to a crisis has minimal influence for the legitimacy of a crisis response. This finding is particularly striking given the theoretical emphasis on the importance of governmental levels in public administration and political science literature (Hooghe and Marks 2003). We can however connect these insights to broader debates in the literature on political-administrative legitimacy, discussing the impact of both decisions and decision-making procedures on citizens' legitimacy perceptions (Brummel and de Blok 2024; Werner & Marien, 2021). Following Esaiasson et al.'s (2019) work on outcome favourability, our non-significant results can be explained by the fact that citizens evaluate the legitimacy of policy decisions more strongly based on their personal policy outcomes rather than institutional or procedural factors, such as the level of government responsible for the decision.

Still, the small effect we find in the Netherlands but not in Germany resonates with the multi-level governance structure of the Netherlands, where authority is more centralized at the national level and provinces have a minor role in emergency management (Groenleer and Hendriks 2020; Hulst 2005). The finding that German respondents are more likely to comply with regional measures from the national government, is also in line with past Covid-19 experiences in Germany (after the second wave), in which the federal government was able to introduce region-specific restrictions after a certain threshold of infections was

reached. These findings suggest that institutional context can be important for how citizens evaluate crisis interventions from different layers of government, providing at least minor evidence for an 'institutional hypothesis' (Schakel and Brown 2022).

Our findings should however be considered in light of several limitations. In the first place, the way in which information is presented in experimental vignettes can have consequences for identifying effects in vignette experiments (cf. Fong and Grimmer 2023). In our study, the fact that protest acceptability was measured after our compliance measures, as well as an additional vignette, may have reduced the salience of the initial treatment, potentially yielding conservative estimates of our treatment effects.

Second, the timing of our experiment may have shaped our results. Because our experiment reflects a scenario of a pandemic outbreak, the recent experience of the Covid-19 pandemic may continue to shape how participants perceive government interventions. Previous research suggests that public attitudes toward such interventions were fluid, with public support declining after the initial phase of the pandemic (Johansson et al. 2021; van der Meer et al. 2023). These attitudes may shift as the memory of Covid-19 fades.

Third, there is a myriad of factors that could impact citizens' acceptance of crisis interventions that our experiment cannot fully account for. For example, the temporality of crisis interventions can become a critical factor in shaping public acceptance, which has become an essential change for many prolonged or 'creeping' crises. When it takes longer for governmental authorities to successfully terminate a crisis situation, this could lead to a decrease in legitimacy of crisis interventions (Boin et al. 2020). Also, the role of 'objective' and nationally implemented threshold criteria—such as the local alert or 'traffic light' systems in various European countries during the pandemic (Wenham et al. 2021)—can play an important role in strengthening the perceived procedural fairness of region-specific interventions. Meanwhile, the complexity of multilevel political systems can create opportunities for blame games, for example, when one tier of government tries to shift blame for crisis responses to another governmental level (Hinterleitner et al. 2022). Such factors can impact the perceived legitimacy of multi-level crisis management in real-life settings.

Fourth, and finally, our focus on one type of transboundary crisis—a pandemic—and two countries—Germany and the Netherlands—has implications for the generalizability of our findings. Particularly, the effect of the governmental level that takes a decision might work differently in multinational states, such as Belgium and Spain, in which multi-level governance is more contested (Keating 1999). Also, the level of compliance with health guidelines varies across countries with different political and cultural characteristics, such as between Southern, Western and Eastern Europe (see e.g. Toshkov 2023). It is further an open question how our findings relate to other transboundary crises, including environmental and/or natural disasters (Ansell et al. 2010) that might be more associated with a single governmental jurisdiction. Future experiments could

test whether our findings are robust for different political systems and different types of transboundary crises, and whether these patterns hold in contexts less influenced by a recent large-scale crisis.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data and materials that support these findings are available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17105574>.

Endnotes

¹ The preregistration of the experiment can be found at https://osf.io/nfvha/?view_only=31d221c11b3b475b9dd567612384cb59.

² We acknowledge the potential risk of hindsight bias, as participants' judgments may have been shaped by their experiences during the real-world Covid-19 pandemic. This reflects a trade-off in our design: while closely mirroring real-world events enhances ecological validity and realism, it also increases the risk of confounding factors such as retrospective evaluations. To mitigate this, we presented the scenario in general terms and avoided explicit references to Covid-19. While such measures cannot eliminate all bias, they help shift participants' focus toward general patterns in crisis governance rather than personal evaluations of actual crisis management.

³ In the context of the Netherlands, it should be noted that regional governance involves more entities than just provincial governments. In recent years, there has been an increasing trend towards new forms of regional governance beyond the provincial level of government, often reflected in forms of inter-municipal collaborations, such as safety regions (*veiligheidsregio's*) or labour market regions (*arbeidsmarktregio's*)—particularly in response to the relatively weak position of provincial governments (Groenleer and Hendriks 2020, 202; see also Hendriks and Michels 2011; Klok et al. 2018). For reasons of comprehensiveness and comparability with German Länder, we have however selected the provincial level of government as one of the conditions in our vignette experiment.

⁴ Compliance has two components—an attitudinal component, that is citizens' stated willingness to comply, and a behavioural component, that is their actual behaviour in accordance with rules and regulations (Levi et al. 2009). In this article, we focus on the attitudinal component of compliance.

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Appendix I

Text of the vignettes in English.

First Part of the Vignette

Condition 1: National Government * National Uniformity

Imagine the following hypothetical situation:

A highly contagious and deadly virus is spreading rapidly in Germany/the Netherlands. For the moment, the infections are concentrated in one region of the country. But it is likely that the virus will spread.

It is up to the national government to decide what measures to take. The national government decides to implement strict rules to contain the spread of the virus: it is no longer allowed to leave your house unless it is absolutely necessary. In addition, schools and businesses are closed.

These rules are applied in the entire territory of the country, including [name of the region], because of the decision of the national government. Hence, in all regions people have to comply with the restrictions.

Think about how you would feel when the national government implements these rules.

Condition 2: National Government * Regional Diversity

Imagine the following hypothetical situation:

A highly contagious and deadly virus is spreading rapidly in Germany/the Netherlands. For the moment, the infections are concentrated in one region of the country. But it is likely that the virus will spread.

It is up to the national government to decide what measures to take. The national government decides to implement strict rules to contain the spread of the virus: it is no longer allowed to leave your house unless it is absolutely necessary. In addition, schools and businesses are closed.

These rules are applied in three regions of the country, including [name of the region], because of the decision of the national government. Hence, in the other regions people do not have to comply with the restrictions.

Think about how you would feel when the national government implements these rules.

Condition 3: Regional Government * National Uniformity

Imagine the following hypothetical situation:

A highly contagious and deadly virus is spreading rapidly in Germany/the Netherlands. For the moment, the infections are concentrated in one region of the country. But it is likely that the virus will spread.

It is up to the regional governments to decide what measures to take. All the regional governments independently decide to implement strict rules to contain the spread of the virus: it is no longer allowed to leave your house unless it is absolutely necessary. In addition, schools and businesses are closed. These rules are applied in the entire territory of the country, including [name of the region], because of the decisions of

the regional governments. Hence, in all regions people have to comply with the restrictions.

Think about how you would feel when the [name of the region] regional government implements these rules.

Condition 4: Regional Government * Regional Diversity

Imagine the following hypothetical situation:

A highly contagious and deadly virus is spreading rapidly in Germany/the Netherlands. For the moment, the infections are concentrated in one region of the country. But it is likely that the virus will spread.

It is up to the regional governments to decide what measures to take. Three regional governments, including yours, independently decide to implement strict rules to contain the spread of the virus: it is no longer allowed to leave your house unless it is absolutely necessary. In addition, schools and businesses are closed. These rules are applied in three regions of the country, including [name of the region], because of the decisions of the regional governments. Hence, in the other regions people do not have to comply with the restrictions.

Think about how you would feel when the [name of the region] regional government implements these rules.

Second Part of the Vignette

Some people in your region do not support the new rules adopted by the [national/regional] government. Protests erupt against the measures, and some of these protests turn violent.

Appendix II

Demographic Distribution of the Samples

	The Netherlands		Germany	
	Sample	Target popul.	Sample	Target popul.
Gender				
Male	46%	50%	52%	50%
Female	54%	50%	47%	50%
Age group				
18–34	22%	29%	28%	26%
35–44	17%	16%	18%	17%
45–54	18%	18%	17%	18%
55–64	21%	18%	20%	20%
65+	23%	20%	17%	20%
Education level				
Basic	16%	15%	18%	20%
Middle	42%	45%	52%	50%
High	43%	40%	30%	30%
Number of valid responses	1120		1132	

Appendix III

Demographic Distribution Across Vignettes

Country	Decision authority	Measure	n	Mean age		Basic education	Secondary education	University education	
				Males	Females				
Germany	Regional	Diversity	282	47 years	52%	48%	21%	52%	26%
		Uniformity	283	46 years	48%	50%	19%	50%	31%
	National	Diversity	286	47 years	52%	48%	18%	51%	31%
		Uniformity	281	47 years	55%	45%	15%	53%	32%
Netherlands	Regional	Diversity	285	50 years	48%	52%	18%	42%	41%
		Uniformity	282	49 years	46%	54%	15%	47%	38%
	National	Diversity	274	50 years	42%	58%	16%	40%	44%
		Uniformity	279	50 years	46%	54%	14%	37%	49%

Appendix IV

Supplementary analyses.

Table A1

TABLE A1 | Compliance: Number of respondents and mean of compliance for experimental groups.

Country	Decision authority	Diversity			Uniformity		
		n	Mean	SD	n	Mean	SD
Germany	Regional	282	3.51	1.16	283	3.72	1.10
	National	286	3.62	1.15	281	3.55	1.18
Netherlands	Regional	285	3.65	1.08	282	3.75	1.12
	National	274	3.81	1.04	279	3.91	1.03

Table A1.1–A4.2

TABLE A1.1 | Compliance: Number of respondents and mean of “Would you adhere to these rules?” item.

Country	Decision authority	Diversity			Uniformity		
		<i>n</i>	Mean	SD	<i>n</i>	Mean	SD
Germany	Regional	282	3.59	1.19	283	3.80	1.12
	National	286	3.71	1.19	281	3.56	1.20
Netherlands	Regional	285	3.67	1.11	282	3.85	1.14
	National	274	3.83	1.07	279	3.96	1.03

TABLE A1.2 | Compliance: Number of respondents and mean of “Would you (not) find it acceptable if citizens disregard these measures?” item.

Country	Decision authority	Diversity			Uniformity		
		<i>n</i>	Mean	SD	<i>n</i>	Mean	SD
Germany	Regional	282	3.42	1.32	283	3.64	1.27
	National	286	3.53	1.38	281	3.53	1.35
Netherlands	Regional	285	3.62	1.25	282	3.65	1.29
	National	274	3.79	1.17	279	3.86	1.21

TABLE A2.1 | Protest unacceptability: Number of respondents and mean protest unacceptability of “Do you (not) think it is fair that people protest...?” item.

Country	Level of measures	Diversity			Uniformity		
		<i>n</i>	Mean	SD	<i>N</i>	Mean	SD
Germany	Regional	282	2.80	1.26	283	2.85	1.27
	National	286	2.74	1.29	281	2.88	1.26
Netherlands	Regional	285	2.82	1.26	282	2.84	1.31
	National	274	2.95	1.31	279	2.96	1.27

TABLE A2.2 | Protest unacceptability: Number of respondents and mean protest unacceptability of “Would you (not) find it acceptable that some people resort to violence...?” item.

Country	Level of measures	Diversity			Uniformity		
		<i>n</i>	Mean	SD	<i>N</i>	Mean	SD
Germany	Regional	282	4.48	0.96	283	4.52	0.92
	National	286	4.30	1.13	281	4.44	1.04
Netherlands	Regional	285	4.61	0.86	282	4.43	1.06
	National	274	4.65	0.85	279	4.62	0.83

TABLE A3 | OLS Regressions of compliance.

Variable	1a	A1a	1b	A1b
Constant	3.505* (0.068)	2.824* (0.171)	3.647* (0.063)	2.547* (0.168)
Uniform	0.214* (0.097)	0.238* (0.097)	0.101 (0.090)	0.113 (0.092)
National	0.117 (0.096)	0.173 (0.096)	0.161 (0.090)	0.186* (0.094)
Uniform × national	−0.290* (0.136)	−0.357* (0.137)	0.003 (0.128)	−0.079 (0.131)
Age		0.010* (0.002)		0.016* (0.002)
Female		0.090 (0.069)		0.073 (0.066)
Other gender		0.528 (0.503)		0.576 (0.735)
Secondary education		0.134 (0.099)		0.191 (0.103)
University education		0.352* (0.110)		0.360* (0.103)
Ideology		−0.119* (0.017)		−0.067* (0.017)
Adjusted R-squared	0.002	0.065	0.005	0.070

TABLE A3.1 | OLS Regressions of compliance: “Would you adhere to these rules?” item.

Variable	1a	A1a	1b	A1b
Constant	3.592* (0.070)	3.012* (0.177)	3.670* (0.064)	2.683* (0.171)
Uniform	0.203* (0.099)	0.224* (0.100)	0.177 (0.091)	0.185* (0.094)
National	0.121 (0.099)	0.163 (0.099)	0.158 (0.092)	0.174 (0.095)
Uniform × national	−0.354* (0.140)	−0.400* (0.141)	−0.042 (0.130)	−0.123 (0.133)
Age		0.007* (0.002)		0.015* (0.002)
Female		0.054 (0.072)		0.084 (0.068)
Other gender		0.320 (0.520)		0.472 (0.749)
Secondary education		0.156 (0.102)		0.098 (0.105)
University education		0.430* (0.114)		0.287* (0.105)
Ideology		−0.099* (0.017)		−0.088* (0.018)
Adjusted R-squared	0.004	0.048	0.007	0.069

TABLE A3.2 | OLS Regressions of compliance: “Would you (not) find it acceptable if citizens disregard these measures?” item.

Variable	1a	A1a	1b	A1b
Constant	3.418* (0.079)	2.636* (0.199)	3.625* (0.073)	2.411* (0.196)
Uniform	0.225* (0.112)	0.252* (0.113)	0.024 (0.103)	0.041 (0.108)
National	0.113 (0.112)	0.183 (0.112)	0.164 (0.104)	0.198 (0.109)
Uniform × national	−0.226 (0.158)	−0.314* (0.160)	0.048 (0.147)	−0.035 (0.153)
Age		0.012* (0.003)		0.017* (0.002)
Female		0.126 (0.081)		0.063 (0.078)
Other gender		0.736 (0.587)		0.681 (0.859)
Secondary education		0.113 (0.115)		0.283* (0.120)
University education		0.273* (0.129)		0.433* (0.120)
Ideology		−0.139* (0.020)		−0.046* (0.020)
Adjusted R-squared	0.001	0.062	0.004	0.053

TABLE A4.1 | OLS regressions of protest unacceptability: “Do you (not) think it is fair that people protest...?” item.

Variable	2a	A2a	2b	A2b
Constant	2.801* (0.076)	2.416* (0.194)	2.818* (0.076)	2.084* (0.207)
Uniform	0.047 (0.107)	0.048 (0.110)	0.026 (0.108)	0.072 (0.114)
National	−0.057 (0.107)	0.019 (0.109)	0.135 (0.109)	0.163 (0.116)
Uniform × national	0.084 (0.151)	0.036 (0.155)	−0.018 (0.154)	−0.104 (0.161)
Age		0.009* (0.003)		0.017* (0.003)
Female		−0.061 (0.079)		0.121 (0.082)
Other gender		1.075 (0.570)		1.397 (0.907)
Secondary education		−0.127 (0.112)		−0.351* (0.127)
University education		−0.006 (0.125)		−0.168 (0.127)
Ideology		−0.085* (0.019)		−0.018 (0.021)
Adjusted R-squared	−0.001	0.030	−0.000	0.054

TABLE A4.2 | OLS regressions of protest unacceptability: “Would you (not) find it acceptable that some people resort to violence...?” item.

Variable	2a	A2a	2b	A2b
Constant	4.475* (0.060)	3.686* (0.151)	4.611* (0.053)	3.674* (0.145)
Uniform	0.041 (0.085)	0.028 (0.086)	-0.185* (0.076)	-0.201* (0.080)
National	-0.178* (0.085)	-0.170* (0.085)	0.039 (0.076)	0.014 (0.081)
Uniform × national	0.107 (0.121)	0.121 (0.121)	0.159 (0.108)	0.169 (0.113)
Age		0.012* (0.002)		0.012* (0.002)
Female		0.164* (0.061)		0.247* (0.058)
Other gender		0.665 (0.444)		-0.111 (0.637)
Secondary education		0.203* (0.087)		0.261* (0.089)
University education		0.172 (0.097)		0.318* (0.089)
Ideology		-0.077* (0.015)		0.005 (0.015)
Adjusted R-squared	0.004	0.062	0.007	0.057

TABLE A5 | Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results for compliance items.

Model	Source of variation	Df	Sum of Sq	Mean Sq	F-value	p-value
Would you adhere to these rules? (Germany)	Uniform	1	0.19	0.19	0.14	0.71
	National	1	0.86	0.86	0.62	0.43
	Uniform × national	1	8.86	8.86	6.41	0.01
	Residuals	1128	1557.87	1.38		
Would you adhere to these rules? (Netherlands)	Uniform	1	6.97	6.97	5.88	0.02
	National	1	5.29	5.29	4.46	0.03
	Uniform × national	1	0.12	0.12	0.10	0.75
	Residuals	1116	1322.02	1.18		
Would you (not) find it acceptable if citizens disregard these measures? (Germany)	Uniform	1	3.52	3.52	1.98	0.16
	National	1	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
	Uniform × national	1	3.61	3.61	2.04	0.15
	Residuals	1128	2000.79	1.77		
Would you (not) find it acceptable if citizens disregard these measures? (Netherlands)	Uniform	1	0.68	0.68	0.45	0.50
	National	1	9.85	9.85	6.51	0.01
	Uniform × national	1	0.16	0.16	0.10	0.75
	Residuals	1116	1688.34	1.51		

Table A6

TABLE A6 | Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results for protest unacceptability items.

Model	Source of variation	Df	Sum of Sq	Mean Sq	F-value	p-value
Would you (not) find it acceptable that some people resort to violence...? (Germany)	Uniform	1	2.55	2.55	2.48	0.12
	National	1	4.40	4.40	4.27	0.04
	Uniform × national	1	0.81	0.81	0.78	0.38
	Residuals	1128	1162.14	1.03		
Would you (not) find it acceptable that some people resort to violence...? (Netherlands)	Uniform	1	3.12	3.12	3.84	0.05
	National	1	3.95	3.95	4.85	0.03
	Uniform × national	1	1.77	1.77	2.17	0.14
	Residuals	1116	908.55	0.81		